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Citation

Giulio Zampogna. Physical Exercise as Treatment for Type 2 Diabetes Distal Symmetric Polyneuropathy: a Systematic Review of Randomized and Controlled Studies. PROSPERO 2020 CRD42020181211 Available from: https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?ID=CRD42020181211

Review question [1 change]

Does physical exercise improve type 2 diabetes distal symmetric polyneuropathy signs or symptoms in humans?

Searches [1 change]

Searches will be conducted (without snowballing references) using Embase, MEDLINE, and Google Scholar databases (no snowballing references) to collect articles published in English within the last eight years (January 1, 2012 - April 20, 2020).

Key search terms:

"type 2 diabetes" , "polyneuropathy" , "exercise"

Types of study to be included [1 change]

Randomized and controlled studies

Condition or domain being studied

Type 2 diabetes distal symmetric polyneuropathy.

Participants/population [1 change]

INCLUDED:

Humans of all ages with type 2 diabetes and distal symmetric polyneuropathy (both conditions clinically diagnosed using recognized criteria, such as those provided by the American Diabetes Association or International Diabetes Federation).

EXCLUDED:

Non-humans; humans with prediabetes, non-type 2 diabetes (e.g., type 1 and gestational), or type 2 diabetes but undiagnosed distal symmetric polyneuropathy.

Intervention(s), exposure(s) [1 change]

Physical exercise of any type must be the main intervention. Studies must provide information on the type, amount, and duration of the exercises performed by study participants.

Comparator(s)/control [1 change]

Must include one of the following:

- No intervention or treatment
- Planned crossover
- Other treatment (e.g., dietary modifications, lifestyle counseling, pharmacotherapy, electrical stimulation, etc.)
- Physical exercise combined with other treatment

Context

N/A

Main outcome(s) [1 change]

Changes in distal symmetric polyneuropathy signs or symptoms measured using validated clinical instruments recommended by the American Diabetes Association.

If restricting inclusion criteria to validated clinical instruments results in fewer than 10 eligible articles, this criterion will be modified to include questionnaires and accessory measurement tools.

***IMPORTANT UPDATE: this portion of the systematic review protocol was modified after search strategy initiation because it was too restrictive and yielded fewer than 10 eligible articles after full-text reviews. The use of validated clinical instruments recommended by the American Diabetes Association was removed as a requirement and, instead, factored into qualitative analyses. The main outcome was modified as follows:

Quantitatively measured changes in signs or symptoms associated with distal symmetric polyneuropathy.

Measures of effect

Variable.

Additional outcome(s)

N/A

Measures of effect

N/A

Data extraction (selection and coding) [1 change]

Studies will be selected for inclusion from search results using three steps: title review, abstract review, and then full-text review. Titles must involve diabetes, exercise (of any type), and neuropathy. Abstracts must indicate that most PICOS elements are satisfied. Full-text reviews must confirm that all PICOS elements are satisfied. Original journal citation reports for each database will be provided alongside a combined version coded with eligibility criteria for each article.

Data to be extracted for thematic synthesis purposes:

- Article citation
- Study design and type
- Objectives / purpose
- Population source/setting and demographics

- Sampling technique and total participants
- Study duration and key time points
- Treatments / interventions
- Measurement tools and parameters
- Primary outcomes
- Secondary outcomes
- Statistical methods
- Results
- Limitations
- Advantages
- Potential themes and knowledge gaps

Risk of bias (quality) assessment [1 change]

Risk of bias assessments will intentionally be excluded from the eligibility criteria to allow the inclusion of all relevant articles in thematic synthesis, thereby preventing study selection bias based on subjective assessments of relative risks of bias (because this systematic review will be conducted by a sole investigator).

Since this systematic review will not include a meta-analysis, confounding of thematic synthesis results due to the inclusion of potentially biased studies will be controlled via qualitative analyses based on the relative strength of PICO criteria fulfillment.

Strategy for data synthesis [1 change]

STRATEGY:

Extracted data will be thematically synthesized based primarily on relationships between interventions and corresponding outcomes, but population characteristics will also be considered. Any proposed theme must be supported by at least two separate studies; findings specific to only one study may be discussed but not presented as a major theme. Discussion of the results may include remarks on the variability in outcome measurement methods, but these will not be themes in of themselves.

RATIONALE:

This systematic review ultimately aims to identify whether or not and in what ways physical exercise could improve distal symmetric polyneuropathy severity in affected type 2 diabetes patients.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

N/A

Contact details for further information

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Organisational affiliation of the review

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Review team members and their organisational affiliations

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Type and method of review [1 change]

Intervention, Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

20 April 2020

Anticipated completion date [1 change]

27 August 2020

Funding sources/sponsors

N/A

Conflicts of interest

Language

English

Country

United States of America

Stage of review [1 change]

Review Completed not published

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2; Exercise; Humans; Polyneuropathies; Research Design

Date of registration in PROSPERO

05 July 2020

Date of first submission

20 April 2020

Stage of review at time of this submission [1 change]

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	Yes
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	Yes
Data extraction	Yes	Yes
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	Yes	Yes
Data analysis	Yes	Yes

Revision note

This systematic review is complete and undergoing initial peer review before submission to journals for publication. The only critical update to the systematic review protocol involved the MAIN OUTCOME(S) portion: this PICO element was modified after search strategy initiation because it was too restrictive and yielded fewer than 10 eligible articles after full-text reviews. The use of validated clinical instruments recommended by the American Diabetes Association was removed as a requirement and, instead, factored into qualitative analyses. The main outcome was modified as follows: Quantitatively measured changes in signs or symptoms associated with distal symmetric polyneuropathy.

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

05 July 2020

27 January 2021